

Impacts of the invasive ascidian *Ciona intestinalis*

Introduction

Ciona intestinalis is an invasive alien ascidian in South African waters. It is found in sheltered areas along the whole South African coast but predominately in harbours. Since it was first reported in Durban in 1955, no impact studies have been conducted on this species.

Aims

To assess the impact of the alien tunicate *C. intestinalis* on biodiversity and composition of indigenous fouling communities, furthermore to test if water movement moderates the impact of this species.

Methods

Treatment plates were subject to removal of *C. intestinalis* every two weeks. Control plates were left in the water untouched for 16 weeks. Two in Saldanha Bay sites were selected, one with high water movement and the other with low water movement. The plates were submerged at two depths, one shallow and one deep.

Results

Conclusion

Preliminary results show that *C. intestinalis* has significant effect on fouling communities and this is moderated by water movement.